

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Musembi**FIRST NAME:** Eunice**PROGRAM CODE:** PHGH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSE PACK

1) INTRODUCTION

ACA-401D period one basically covered the standards of international academic writing skills through use of proper English and the right rules of style. The main focus was on the differences between United Kingdom (UK) and United States (US) English. Majorly, the focus was on the spelling, punctuation, citations, plagiarism and logical flow in writing using simple and clear English words. This period involved reading materials such as the Course Pack and video presentations by various presenters and authors. The course pack offers a clear roadmap for essay writing by sharing the key steps to follow as well as the language, grammar, words to use with very well guided examples such as the resume. Strawman fallacy was well explained by Joseph Wu of the University of Cambridge and Paul Henne of the University of Duke. This was the first time I heard about the Straw Man Fallacy analogy and I keenly followed to understand what it is and its application in real life situation, this one I learnt a lot. Two other videos by Allicia Williams, 2017 and Dr Christopher Medalisa, 2015 focused on education accreditation in the U.S. which I thought was a very good information for someone looking for a school.

2) REACTION TO THE BOOK

a) Essay writing

The coursepack, ACA-401/ACA-401D 2019, covered a wide variety of key concepts that have to be considered while writing an essay from developing the essay to ensuring appropriate referencing as well as use of proper English.

Essay writing is not a linear process (EUCLID 2019, 1). Essay writing involves a series of many steps that requires time to read, research, thinking and writing. One is expected to fully understand the topic they are writing about and this can only be achieved through reading many documents related to the topic in question. I have worked in the management of public health programs and for the program to be considered successful, the data collected during the process of program implementation must be validated and analyzed. The validation process is very important as it justifies that the data is genuine and valid and that it's a true reflection of the performance of the indicator being monitored. The analysis of the data shows the trend and if the indicator has moved from one level to another, it will show an upward or downward trend when a line graph is drawn. Likewise, essay writing can only be successful if the material gathered is analyzed and responding to the essay questions as required.

Creative thinking and critical thinking are to be embraced while writing an essay (EUCLID 2019, 2). Creative thinking is about having diversified ideas through mind mapping, brainstorming asking the why questions. Critical thinking helps in narrowing the many ideas generated to what is relevant to the essay questions. Just like in a data collection process, a lot of data is collected, but only what is relevant to the indicator being tracked is used. This helps one to remain focused and not to give information that is irrelevant to what is asked. As such, there will be need to a lot of editing of the work to ensure it meets all the requirements. My current focus in the health sector is in quality of health care improvement, creative and critical thinking comes in handy here while doing the root because analysis of the gaps identified in the system. Many responses will be given through various methods such as the brain storming, process mapping, the use of the 5-Whys etc. a decision matrix is then used to narrow down and to prioritize on what is relevant for the program to focus on improving and what will have a great impact to the quality of care improvement.

You have not completed your assignment until you have handed it in (EUCLID 2019, 4). I have been working in donor funded programs for more than 10 years. The work involves report writing on a monthly, quarterly, biannual and annual basis to show progress of the activities being implemented as well as how the finances are being utilized. The report is usually done and proofread by several program advisors so as to ensure that it meets the standards of the donor. The program always has a due date for when the reports should be sent and a contact person whom the reports should be send to. All the other activities would be stopped to ensure the report is ready for sending by the due date, otherwise, the program would be given a warning for its termination if it does not adhere

to the set deadlines. Just like the program work, any assignment should be taken seriously and the student should have all the information regarding when the assignment should be handed in, to whom and other details such as formatting in order to ensure he/she is not finalized for not following the set guidelines.

b) Plagiarism

Plagiarism is wrong, unethical, it is punishable, and it is a serious academic offence. (EUCLID 2019, 4, 5). Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source information (EUCLID 2019, 5). This happens when a writer takes someone else's words or ideas such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying and pasting from the internet and or having someone write a paper for you and then putting your name on it and submitting as your own work (ibid.). To avoid plagiarism, it is a must for everyone to cite the source of the information through proper referencing. In my program work while doing data collection in the field, it is a must to quote the data source and this must be reflected in the report. This helps in validation of the data just in case someone doubts it, it also gives credit to the people who generated the data. I have seen preachers quote the bible verses including the name of the book, the chapter and the verse while preaching so as to make it easy for the congregants to follow and also to make references. I think, citing and reference is very key not just for the writer, but also for the reader as they are able to make cross reference of the written material for better understanding.

c) Paraphrasing

Paraphrasing of the original work helps to avoid many quotes in the written work. (EUCLID 2019, 8). It is also important to note that, the paraphrased sentence should carry the same message as the original one to avoid misrepresentation. Joseph Wu, University of Cambridge in his video defines Strawman fallacy to be when an opponent's position is misrepresented to make it easier to critique by either oversimplifying what is being discussed or answering a question that one has not been asked. Paul Henne, Duke University in his video presentation also states that, Strawman Fallacy could be intentional or non-intentional. As a result of poor paraphrasing, strawman fallacy could result.

Writing that does not sound right, will not read right (EUCLID 2019, 16). I grew up in very remote part of Kenya and schooled in the remotest schools as well. Composition writing was part of the English learning. Any time we would write it, the teacher encouraged us to read it aloud to see if it would flow, for us that time", English was English "since our teachers pronounced every English word with a mother tongue dialect in it. Correct English started unfolding when I joined my O levels in a provincial school that had native English-speaking teachers. I knew my primary school teachers had tried, now this was pure English! Although I struggled to catch up, finally I made it and am happy today I know the difference between the "country English" and the right English that would flow when written and or when spoken. In this reading. I have also learned the difference between American and British English, something I never knew before. Repetition of

words makes the reading boring and monotonous (EUCLID 2019, 41), Therefore, it is advisable to use different words consecutively that carry the same meaning to communicate the same message. This adds flavor to the flow of the writing than repeating one word all through in one paragraph. Skills on sentence construction, word choice, grammar and proper use of punctuation marks are very essential when composing a clear write up. (EUCLID 2019, 42). In order to attract readers to your work, or make your reading interesting, the writer should always try to start the papers with a hook and end with a reference (ibid.). Just like a well written resume will make one get shortlisted for an interview, as well, a well written paper will win many to read it.

d) Use of abbreviations

Abbreviations should be used only in contexts where they are clear to the readers. (EUCLID 2019, 44). Acronyms must be introduced when first used in the text through placing the acronym in parentheses and there after using the acronym (ibid.). Writing the word in full and putting the acronym in the parentheses makes reading easier for the readers. It should not be assumed that everybody understands all the acronyms in the 'world'. During my project work and report writing, I have learnt that, it is advisable to first introduce any acronym by writing it in full the first time you are using the word and then putting the acronym in the parentheses immediately after the word. Later, the acronym can be used comfortably within the text. The acronym is also, introduced at the front pages of the write up in the explanation of the abbreviations page. This prepares the reader of the acronyms to expect within the text and what they stand for. Abbreviations fully acceptable on envelopes and mailing labels should rarely be used in addresses in running texts as they can cause confusion such as U.S. and US. (EUCLID 2019, 45). In business, formal and technical writing, use of the English equivalent of the abbreviation is encouraged in order to avoid misinterpretation by the readers (EUCLID 2019, 56).

3) CONCLUSION

It is best to create content using "plain English" principles. Plain language involves use of short sentences with simple words and discourages use of jargon, acronyms and abbreviations. It should be visually inviting, logically organized and understandable on the first reading (ibid.). This reading was a great eye-opener in terms of understanding the basics of writing a successful essay. It clearly demonstrates the dos and the don'ts as well as the difference between the American and Great Britain English.

Being a beginner in the doctoral studies, this course pack lays a solid foundation for writing principles by stating the key issues to consider while writing an essay from drafting the essay plan to writing, researching (literature review) to submitting a fully refined paper. As much as this is a topic for the first period, I will keep on referring to it the rest of my coursework including drafting, writing and final submission of my doctoral thesis. The examples given to guide the proper writing skills are so relevant to life such as the resume writing. Clearly, a poorly written resume cannot get one shortlisted for an interview. In that case, is it possible for a student to pass their graduate studies with a poorly

written essay or thesis? Definitely not. To succeed in the doctoral studies, one has to master proper writing skills by adhering to what has been covered in this course pack. I particularly enjoyed reading the course pack on essay writing explaining the dos and the don'ts for writing an essay and the examples given to guide on proper writing particular the use of transition words and the resume. This was so relevant to my doctoral studies. The two videos by Joseph Wu (University of Cambridge) and Paul Henne (University of Duke) played a very key role in helping me understand why poor paraphrasing is bad by using the strawman fallacy analogy.

Alicia Williams, 2017, in her video presentation explained about the distance education accrediting commission and its importance. Dr Christopher Medalisa, 2015, shared about the accreditation of U.S. education. As much as these two presentations may not look relevant to this course, I found them quite informative to a student who is searching for a school for higher learning. One of the key factors or criteria to look for is if the school is accredited by higher education to offer the courses one would like to do. Quality assurance for higher education is very important to study in a school that is well recognized by the authorizing body. Before Joining Euclid University, I did my own due diligence just to be sure the university is authorized to teach the courses it offers and if the degree that I will get from here will be recognized after graduation.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.